

Mannich Bases of Coumaran-3-Ones

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Mannich bases from 5-chloro-, 7-chloro-, 5-methyl- and 7-methyl-coumaran-3-ones have been prepared with a view to testing them for their physiological activity on lower organisms.

SEVERAL new Mannich bases have been synthesised as hydrochlorides (I) from substituted coumaran-3-ones^{1,2}. Interesting biological activity against lower organisms is expected from these bases as they are related to those from chroman-4-ones³.

In the present investigation, coumaran-3-ones were obtained from phenoxy acetic acids, according to the method of Minton et. al¹, with minor changes. Phenoxy acetic acids were first converted into their acid chlorides which were then cyclised, in the cold, with anhydrous aluminium chloride.

The Mannich reaction on Coumaran-3-ones was done according to the method described in the literature⁴. Dry benzene was used as solvent and the reaction mixture was acidified with a couple of drops of AR-hydrochloric acid.

Lower yields of the coumaran-3-ones and their slower Mannich reaction (6-8 hr.) were essentially due to their appreciable 'enol' form (II) present. In the p.m.r. spectrum of 5-nitro-coumaran-3-one in DMSO *d*₆, enol form was present in about 90% which explained its appreciable water solubility and lower yields in Mannich reactions. However the IR spectrum clearly showed strong band at 1720 cm⁻¹ (3-ketone group) and it slowly yielded conventional derivatives like 2, 4-dinitrophenyl-hydrazone and oxime.

All the Mannich bases (as hydrochlorides) were found to be stable and could be isolated from their aqueous solutions. The free bases have been characterised through their picrates.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infrared (model 337) spectrophotometer using KBr discs. PMR spectrum was recorded with a Varian A 60 D instrument

for solutions in CDCl₃ or DMSO *d*₆ containing TMS as internal reference. Reactions were followed by the plates. All the m. pts. are uncorrected.

5-or 7-(Chloro or methyl)-coumaran-3-ones: *o*- or *p*-Chloro or methyl phenoxyacetyl chloride (10 tg., obtainable by the action of thionylchloride on the corresponding phenoxyacetic acids) was dissolved in dry benzene (30-50 ml.) and finely powdered aluminium chloride (10 g.) was added slowly with vigorous stirring at 0°. The reaction mixture was left stirring at 0° for 4-hr. It was then poured over crushed ice (250 g) and after acidification with hydrochloric acid (5 N), it was extracted with ether (3×100 ml) and washed first with aqueous bicarbonate (5%, 3×50 ml.) and later with cold water (3×50 ml.) and on drying over sodium sulphate, the solvent was removed. The crude products were distilled in vacuo. The distillate slowly solidified to pure coumaran-ones (yields 50-60%) $\nu_{\max}$ at 1720 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl) and 1605 cm⁻¹ (unsaturation)

5-Nitro-coumaran-3-one: M. p. 151°-52°; $\nu_{\max}$ at 1720 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl), 1650 cm⁻¹ (enol) and 1605 cm⁻¹ (unsaturation); p. m. r. signals at τ 4.5 (1 H_s, OH, 90%), τ 2.9 (1 H_d, $\tau = 7.5$, = CH) and τ 2.0 (3H, aromatic protons); 2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone, m p. 140°-41°.

Mannich reaction: A mixture of substituted coumaran-3-one (0.01 M), and paraformaldehyde (0.01 M) in dry benzene was heated under reflux for 30 min. To this was added appropriate secondary amine hydrochloride (0.01 M). The reaction mixture was acidified with a few drops of conc. HCl and refluxed for 6-8 hr, during which most of the Mannich bases (I) separated out as hydrochlorides in crystalline form. The reaction mixture was cooled, filtered and the product obtained was washed with dry benzene and recrystallised from absolute ethanol.

The Mannich bases (as hydrochlorides) were soluble in warm water and are stable. They were characterised through their picrates.

The free bases were sticky compounds, which could not be crystallised.

TABLE-STRUCTURE (I)

Sl. No.	R ¹	-NR ₂	Yield%	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	%N		Picrate M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	%N	
						Found	Calcd			Found	Calcd
1.	5-Chloro.	Morpholino	78	248	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ NO ₃ Cl.HCl	4.69	4.60	178	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₁₀ N ₄ Cl	11.41	11.28
2.	"	Piperidino	65	195	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ NO ₃ Cl.HCl	4.58	4.64	145	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₉ N ₇ Cl	11.10	11.29
3.	"	Dimethylamino	47	216-7	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ NO ₃ Cl.HCl	4.97	5.30	176-7	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₈ N ₄ Cl	11.89	12.32
4.	"	Diethylamino	43.5	151-2	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ NO ₃ Cl.HCl	4.83	4.83	170	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₉ N ₄ Cl	11.51	11.67
5.	7-Chloro-	Morpholino	69.6	185-6	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ NO ₃ Cl.HCl	4.54	4.60	156	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₁₀ N ₄ Cl	10.99	11.28
6.	"	Piperidino	63.7	181	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ NO ₃ Cl.HCl	4.70	4.64	141-2	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₉ N ₄ Cl	11.34	11.29
7.	"	Dimethylamino	42.8	206-7	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ NO ₃ Cl.HCl	5.02	5.30	152-3	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₈ N ₄ Cl	11.61	12.32
8.	"	Diethylamino	38.4	211.2	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ NO ₃ Cl.HCl	4.62	4.83	176-7	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₉ N ₄ Cl	11.83	11.67
9.	5-Methyl-	Morpholino	45.6	221-2	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ NO ₃ .HCl	4.82	4.94	191	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₁₀ H ₄	11.58	11.76
10.	"	Piperidino	33	203-4	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₃ .HCl	5.11	4.97	172-2	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₉ N ₄	11.39	11.81
11.	"	Dimethylamino	24.5	183.4	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃ .HCl	5.84	5.79	147-8	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₉ N ₄	13.11	12.90
12.	"	Diethylamino	18	195.6	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO ₃ .HCl	5.29	5.16	143-8	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₉ N ₄	12.08	12.12
13.	7-Methyl-	Morpholino	38.6	240	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ NO ₃ .HCl	4.78	4.94	209-10	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₁₀ N ₄	11.38	11.76
14.	"	Piperidino	42.4	231-2	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₃ .HCl	4.91	4.97	182-3	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₉ N ₄	11.92	11.81
15.	"	Dimethylamino	22	192	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃ .HCl	5.49	5.79	152-3	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₉ N ₄	12.00	12.90
16.	"	Diethylamino	24.5	210	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO ₃ .HCl	5.32	5.16	172-3	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₉ N ₄	11.94	12.12

The m. ps., analysis, yields of the Mannich bases and their picrates are shown in the Table.

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